

A Critical Discussion of the Second Language Motivational Self-System Model

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to provide a critical discussion of the Second Language Motivational Self-System (L2MSS) model and the implications of this model for language teaching research and practice. While the L2MSS is considered one of the most influential models in L2 motivation research, its utility has recently been questioned. In this discussion, the background to the L2MSS and related concepts is provided. Current critical issues in relation to the model are then discussed, and avenues for future research are suggested. Implications for L2 classroom practice are also provided.

Keywords: L2 learning, L2 motivation, L2 Motivational Self-System

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a broad construct which has been defined by numerous scholars. Although motivation plays a key role in the success of mastering a second language (Al-Hoorie & Szabó, 2022; Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021), there is still no consensus about its definition (Alamer, 2024), because motivation interacts with many other

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factors, such as intellectual ability, learning and cognitive styles. In this critical discussion, motivation will be defined as:

the dynamically changing cumulative arousal in a person that initiates, directs, coordinates, amplifies, terminates, and evaluates the cognitive and motor processes whereby initial wishes and desires are selected, prioritised, operationalised and acted out (Dörnyei and Ottó (1998, p. 65)

This definition emphasizes the fluctuating nature of motivation and learners' wishes and desires for both the present and the future, the priorities they give to these wishes and desires, and what they actually do (or avoid doing) to enact these wishes and desires.

Most theories and models of L2 motivation originate from social and cognitive psychology. Notable amongst these is Gardner's (1985) socio-educational model, which is associated with two well-known concepts: instrumental orientation (the benefits gained from learning a language) and integrative orientation (the desire to learn a language in order to be part of a group and identify with members of that group). An important approach to L2 motivation also comes from self-determination theory (Noels, 2001; Ryan & Deci, 2000), which explains the degree of internalization of motivation, from extrinsic motivation (an external goal for learning a language such as passing an exam or getting a job) to intrinsic motivation (an internal desire to learn a language) of a language learner's behaviour, and the extent of their engagement in learning (Hiver, 2022; Mercer, 2022; Oga-Baldwin & Hirosawa, 2022). In contrast, Dörnyei's (2009) L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) is based on the notion of the self, that is, the beliefs a person holds about themselves and the responses of others to the person.

While the socio-educational model, self-determination theory and the L2MSS have all been influential in L2 motivation research, the latter has achieved the broadest recognition. The L2MSS has been successfully used in monolingual and multilingual contexts around the globe (Henry & Liu, 2023), in relation not only to L2, but also to L3 (third language) learning (Csizér, 2019; Huang et al., 2015; Wang & Liu, 2017). In terms of research, studies informed by the L2MSS have been numerous (Yousefi & Mahmoodi, 2022) and have become mainstream (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021). The model's utility (Al-Hoorie, 2018; Yousefi & Mahmoodi, 2022) and predictive capacity (Papi et al., 2019) have been statistically demonstrated. Moreover, and probably most importantly, the L2MSS has moved from mainly quantitatively-oriented approaches to qualitative inquiries into L2 motivation.

Although the L2MSS has received much attention, there have also been critical appraisals of this model. The key focal point of these appraisals has been whether the motivation for learning a second or other languages can be modelled as a self-system (Al-Hoorie et al., 2023; Henry & Liu, 2023, 2024). To address this question, the current critical discussion will first introduce the L2MSS and then engage in a critical evaluation of this model. Based on this evaluation, implications for future motivation research and pedagogy will be considered.

THE L2 MOTIVATIONAL SELF SYSTEM (L2MSS)

The L2MSS explores learners' reasons for learning a language in terms of their view of who they would like to become in the future through their use of the language; their perceptions of what other people think they should do to become that person; and how their learning experiences impact on their motivational behaviours. The concept of 'self' is central to the L2MSS. The concept of self refers to a person's mental images of themselves based on their thoughts and feelings. It is a repertoire of beliefs, evaluations and perceptions which form a person's identity in relation to the world around them (Mercer, 2011). In addition to personality traits and physical characteristics (Dörnyei, 2020), the self is also influenced by sociocultural, educational and personal contexts. The L2MSS is informed by two theories of self: possible selves (Markus & Nurius, 1986), and self-discrepancy (Higgins, 1987). Possible selves are defined as (Markus & Nurius, 1986) future selves:

that are hoped for [that] might include the successful self, the creative self, the rich self, the thin self, or the loved and admired self, whereas the dreaded possible selves could be the alone self, the depressed self, the incompetent self, the alcoholic self, the unemployed self, or the bag lady self (p.954).

Possible selves can be understood as being future-oriented, multifaceted, and dynamic. In terms of being future-oriented, possible selves are the self-images that represent individuals' ideas of what they might become, what they would like to become, and what they are afraid of becoming. Thus, possible selves act as a future self-guide. With regard to multi-facetedness, possible selves involve visions (Dörnyei & Chan, 2013), such as thoughts, images, goals, aspirations and fears. Possible selves are also dynamic because they are "not well-anchored in social experience; (...) comprises the self-knowledge that is most vulnerable and responsive to changes in the environment" (Markus & Nurius, 1986, p. 956).

Understanding these characteristics of possible selves is necessary to follow critiques of the L2MSS, which will be discussed later in this article.

The concept of possible selves is linked with motivational behaviour in self-discrepancy theory (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011). In self-discrepancy theory, the analysis of the self begins with three basic domains: the actual self, which is the current attributes that someone possesses; the ideal self, which is the attributes someone would ideally like to possess; and the ought-to self, which is the attributes that someone believes they ought to possess. Higgins (1998) emphasised that the ideal self has a promotion focus, which is related to positive emotional-motivational predispositions such as hopes, aspirations, advancement, growth and accomplishment, and the ought-to self has a prevention focus, which is concerned with protection, safety, responsibilities and obligations. Self-discrepancy theory (Higgins, 1987) posits that these selves have a motivational function because discrepancies between one's current self and these future selves lead to discomfort, and this discomfort motivates a person to increase the harmony between the two selves in order to reduce this feeling of discomfort.

Drawing on possible selves and self-discrepancy theory, the first two constructs of the L2MSS (Dörnyei, 2009, p. 29) are:

The *Ideal L2 Self*, which is the L2-specific facet of one's 'ideal self': if the person we would like to become speaks an L2, the '*ideal L2 self*' is a powerful motivator to learn the L2 because of the desire to reduce the discrepancy between our actual and ideal selves.

The *Ought-to L2 Self*, which concerns the attributes that one believes one *ought to* possess to meet expectations, and to *avoid* possible negative outcomes.

The third key construct of the L2MSS is related to the learning situation and is conceptualised as:

The *L2 Learning Experience*, which concerns situated, 'executive' motives related to the immediate learning environment and experience (e.g. the impact of the teacher, the curriculum, the peer group, the experience of success) (Dörnyei, 2009, p. 29).

The L2MSS represents an attempt to comprehensively synthesise previous L2 motivational thinking by fully embracing the psychological notion of the self. It is

seen not only as a natural progression from the socio-educational model (Dörnyei, 2010) but also has become the most dominant theoretical framework in L2 motivation research (Boo et al., 2015). This dominance can be attributed to its adaptable and flexible nature, which supplies “fertile ground for innovation and reflection across various English language learning contexts” (Yousefi & Mahmoodi, 2022, p. 3).

Since the initial proposal of the L2MSS in 2005 and its full elaboration in 2009, numerous empirical studies have been carried out to test its validity in various learning contexts, which has enabled it to gain broad acceptance. For example, Yousefi and Mahmoodi (2022) conducted a meta-analysis based on 17 published L2 motivation studies. They found that approaching L2 motivation through the lens of L2 possible selves (ideal and/or ought-to) in the classroom contributed to L2 learners’ learning development because students who have a ‘future time orientation’ tend to create longer-term goals and are motivated by precise, anticipated events (Dörnyei, 2020).

In relation to the L2MSS, the concept of ‘visions’, a synonym for L2 possible selves, began to find its way into discussions of L2 motivation and classroom teaching practices through practitioner-oriented publications (Al-Murtadha, 2019; Gregersen & MacIntyre, 2014; Hadfield & Dörnyei, 2013; Mackay, 2019; Vlaeva & Dörnyei, 2021). As Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) pointed out, “vision is one of the single most important factors within the domain of language learning: where there is a vision, there is a way” (p. 2). They highlight the use of visions to explain long-term efforts to master an L2. Although this vision-based view of motivation is promising, a number of conditions need to be realized for it to achieve its potential, such as the L2 possible selves being accompanied by action plans and effective procedural strategies and being offset by counteracting feared possible selves.

Ongoing development of the conceptualization of L2 future possible selves has led to further refinements of the L2MSS, such as the “anti-ought-to self” (a language learner’s desire to go against societal expectations and norms) (Thompson, 2017), the “rooted L2 self” (a heritage-oriented concept which is defined by a migrant’s strong feelings of connection to speakers of heritage languages and which can be tied to specific individuals or more generally to a defined community) (MacIntyre et al., 2017); the “plurilingual future self” (a concept which fosters positive attitudes towards language diversity and plurilingual aspirations) (Busse, 2017); and the “ideal multilingual self” (a notion which encourages a move away from a monolingual mindset to a multilingual motivational framework) (Henry, 2017).

With these continuing refinements, the L2MSS has become one of the most successful motivational frameworks in terms of theoretical advancements and teaching practices in the area of L2 motivation.

A CRITICAL EVALUATION OF THE L2MSS

This critical discussion addresses the question of whether L2 motivation can be modelled as a self-system, given the increasing realisation that the self is a complex dynamic system (Mercer, 2012) and given the complexity of motivation (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021). A justification for modelling L2 motivation as a self-system seems to be absent from Dörnyei's scholarship (Henry & Liu, 2023).

The main criticism of the L2MSS is that it is hard to conceptualise the self as a stable concept. MacIntyre (2022) critiqued the L2MSS by arguing that “the self is one of the most notoriously nebulous concepts in the social sciences” (p. 90) due to its “multi-dimensional, multifaceted dynamic structure that is systematically implicated in all aspects of social information processing” (Markus & Wurf, 1987, p. 301). Although the L2MSS is based on a conceptualization of the self as active and dynamic and on motivational fluctuations taking place in students' learning (Dörnyei, 2020), in practice, many L2 motivation studies only focus on the utility and application of the model, viewing the L2MSS as a stable psychological construct (Yousefi & Mahmoodi, 2022). These studies have examined either the predictive validity of the L2MSS by exploring how the selves predict motivation and behaviour or the relationship between the selves and L2 proficiency achievement (Papi, 2022). Standardised instruments, such as surveys, have been used to measure learners' motivation. For example, Dörnyei and Ushioda (2021) presented patterns and relationships across a large data set for the L2 Learning Experience to explain learners' motivation. The practice of using standardised measures, however, is inconsistent with the view of motivation as being complex and fluid. Thus, some scholars (Al-Hoorie et al., 2023; Henry & Liu, 2023, 2024; MacIntyre & Serroul, 2015) have started questioning the validity of the L2MSS, or more specifically, the concept of self used as the theoretical base for the Ideal L2 Self and the Ought-to L2 Self. For example, MacIntyre (2022) has suggested the L2MSS should only be applied in situations where the self has become a prominent and salient concern of the conscious mind.

This criticism of the self-concept has been taken up by Henry and Liu (2023), who argue that the conceptualization of self at the core of the L2MSS “remains the elephant in the room” (p. 2). They discuss five problem areas associated with this

conceptualization: the fantasy problem (where there is no differentiation between desire and fantasy, desire being a wish that can be achieved, and fantasy being something that is not realistic); the ought-to L2 self problem (where there is no specificity about the relevant others whose views should be followed); the integrativeness problem (the difficulty of incorporating affiliation motives into the learner's goals and wishes, such as being a member of a particular target language community); the learning experience problem (failure to consider diverse experiences of L2 learning and acquisition); and the context problem (the difficulty of identifying interactions which impact on students' motivation in specific classroom environments).

In addition, the disproportionate research emphasis on L2 possible selves but not on the L2 learning experiences has been critiqued (Al-Hoorie, 2018). Although the imagined self predicts imagined efforts very well, the L2MSS needs to be more firmly grounded in learning experiences, learning behaviours and language outcomes (Al-Hoorie, 2018). This includes learners' in and out of class learning experiences, learners' interactions with peers and teachers, what is taught, materials that have been used, and how learning is assessed (Al-Hoorie, 2018). The L2 Learning Experience, thus, is an umbrella term that covers many aspects of the learning situation. The main reason behind the neglect of L2 learning experiences is that, unlike the first two constructs, which were built on well-established theories in social psychology, the L2 Learning Experience was theorised from immediate learning situations and was only described in a few lines in Dörnyei's (Dörnyei, 2009) original formulation without detailed elaboration. (See Dörnyei's definition of the L2 Learning Experience cited above).

In response to criticism of the lack of attention to L2 learning experiences, Dörnyei (2019) borrowed the notion of engagement in educational psychology. He used this to redefine the L2 Learning Experience as "the perceived quality of the learners' engagement with various aspects of the language learning process" (p. 26) and demonstrated how this engagement-centred approach, drawing on relevant measurement resources developed in educational psychology, could be applied in L2 motivation studies. Other researchers, such as Hiver (2022), and Oga-Baldwin and Hirosawa (2022), have taken up this initiative and have further discussed the potential of engagement as a construct in L2 motivation research. For example, Mercer (2022) outlines three possible focuses: the teaching/learning context, process and temporality, and task-level motivation. These focuses, which represent a more complex and dynamic view of motivation, are not always considered in discussions of the L2MSS.

In a similar vein, drawing on a positive psychology lens, a holistic and domain-specific scale for measuring the L2 Learning Experience that focuses on six dimensions (e.g. positive emotions, negative emotions, engagement, relationship, meaning and accomplishment) has been proposed by Li (2023). In addition to this development, other studies have looked at the influence of the L2 Learning Experience to further explore this component on learners' L2 motivation, such as the effects of online L2 learning experiences (Wang, 2022), learning approaches (Irgatoğlu, 2021), and teaching approaches (Yang & Liang-Itsara, 2024).

The criticisms discussed above, in essence, suggest that a general framework like the L2MSS, may lack flexibility and specificity to accommodate the complexities of L2 motivation of particular individuals in particular contexts. In order to accommodate these complexities, more personal and context-oriented research approaches, such as a small lens perspective and a person-in-context perspective, are necessary. For example, Ushioda (2022) argues that future research needs to take into account local classroom realities and wider institutional and societal discourses which impact learners' motivation to engage with L2 learning at any particular moment in time, instead of simply translating theory and research into generalizable and decontextualized principles. Doing so would enable the investigation of dynamic processes of motivational change to be placed within an individual person's learning experience or within a person-in-context relational view of motivation (Ushioda, 2009). This would place a focus on the agency of the individual student as a thinking, feeling human being, rather than a static construct; a focus on the interaction between learners and their learning contexts, rather than independent categories and a focus on a relational, instead of a linear, perspective on motivation. This would do justice to L2 motivation as an organic process that emerges through a complex system of interrelations. This person-in-context relational view echoes perspectives on L2 motivation in relation to learners' environments or social worlds.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Research into the L2MSS needs to take account of the issues raised in the previous section of this paper. An example of research that does take these issues into account is the current wave of research into L2 motivation from a complex dynamic systems perspective (see, for example, Papi & Hiver, 2020; Hiver et al., 2023). However, the complex dynamic systems perspective faces challenges as to how the L2 self as a psychological concept, with its multi-faceted nature, complex

connections with learning environments, and unpredictability during the learning process, can be conceptualised to be methodologically researchable. Dörnyei (2020), in considering the possible application of the dynamic systems perspective to the study of motivation, characterizes these challenges in terms of the conceptualisation of motivation and motivational dynamics. The key issue has been how to define L2 motivation, which was traditionally considered a stable personal trait, then a situation-specific state that is transitory and temporary, and now, currently, an ever-evolving process with constant ebbs and flows. Further, when L2 motivation is conceptualised in a process-oriented manner, there is unease about relating motivation to time, as traditional psychological theories treat time as a general construct rather than something that is subject to change. To add to the complexity of these challenges, the influence of society, the impacts of situational learning, emotions and affect, and conscious and unconscious motivation, all contribute to motivational dynamics.

These complex motivational dynamics present new research frontiers, but these frontiers have also deterred many scholars, resulting in a generally slow response in L2 motivation research to address them (Dörnyei, 2020). In order to move out of this impasse, several scholars (Hiver & Al-Hoorie, 2020; Papi & Hiver, 2020) have suggested how L2 motivation research can further draw on complex dynamic systems theory (CDST) principles. In a nutshell, a CDST perspective takes a holistic approach that assumes “the combined and interactive operation of a number of different factors relevant to a specific situation rather than following the traditional practice of examining cause-effect relations between isolated variables” (Dörnyei, 2020, p. 42), and recognises “the individuality of learning trajectories” and re-assigns “responsibility for development from cognition alone to an agentive socio-cognitive process” (Hiver et al., 2023, p. 3). Research which draws on the constructs making up the L2MSS (the Ideal L2 Self, the Ought-to L2 Self and the L2 Learning Experience), thus, needs to avoid treating these constructs as being fixed, stable and independent of each other and instead focus on multiplicity, dynamism, change and relations between each construct. This more dynamic approach would enable the L2MSS to be conceptualized less as a static model and more as a dynamic system.

Methodological innovations also need to keep pace with this CDST perspective to ensure that when conducting L2 motivation research, “everything counts, everything is counted and everything changes” (Li et al., 2023, p. 553). In this respect, longitudinal designs with dense observations of a learner’s performance

are desirable, so the process of individual learners' development can be understood (Hiver et al., 2023).

Longitudinal and ethnographic research designs have been taken up in a number of L2 learner motivation studies (Consoli, 2024; Doiz & Lasagabaster, 2018; Fryer & Roger, 2018; Gundarina, 2023; Kikuchi, 2019; Tajabadi & Consoli, 2024). These studies illustrate that longitudinal designs can accommodate qualitatively oriented research tools, such as case studies, narratives, individual interviews, focus groups, and deep observations, enabling researchers to add a human dimension to impersonal data, such as statistics. These research approaches allow participants to talk freely about their beliefs, contradictions, individual differences and personal experiences in various learning contexts over a period of time. These approaches enable L2 motivation to be regarded not only as an individual attribute (Kikuchi, 2019), but also as a social construction (Lamb, 2016): That is, "we come to strive for certain things in life as a result of our socialization in a particular community or society, and the extent to which we can act on our desires is also constrained by our social environment" (Lamb, 2016, p. 324). This perspective resonates with the current view of L2 motivation as a social practice (García, 2022; Poehner, 2022; Ushioda, 2022), and could also be applied to L2MSS studies.

Such studies are also expanding the research frontier in terms of research contexts, research participants, and data elicitation techniques. For example, they are examining students' development and trajectories of their L2 selves using a small-lens perspective (Ushioda, 2016) to examine language learning settings, such as English medium instruction (EMI) programs (Doiz & Lasagabaster, 2018), study abroad programs (Fryer & Roger, 2018) and migrant English immersion programs (Gundarina, 2023). Based on detailed observations of these research settings, the findings reveal that students' formation of their L2 selves and trajectories of L2 motivation are highly context-dependent. For example, Gundarina's (2023) study explores migrant children's ideal selves and learning motivation. Applying a drawing-based elicitation technique, the study challenges earlier claims that children are not mature enough to have a clear future possible self. The study shows how middle-school children in an English immersion program express diverse, at times pragmatic and practical, but remarkably clear ideal selves. Although these studies do not utilize the L2MSS, these qualitative approaches to understanding L2 selves and student motivation could also be drawn on in L2MSS research.

However, it should be stressed that, as Al-Hoorie and Hiver (2022) point out, “qualitative research designs do not by themselves guarantee a more complex and dynamic perspective for research, particularly if the research design is not inherently connected to or informed by the conceptual framework of complexity” (p. 183). Both qualitative and quantitative designs have an important role to play in L2MSS research. Importantly, quantitative methods in L2MSS research need to move beyond generalisation, comparisons of groups and measurements of linear relationships, and be more diversified, for example, by analysing variation at different levels and timescales, paying attention to temporal processes, applying spatial analysis and studying networked phenomena nested in contexts (Hiver & Al-Hoorie, 2020). Thus, selecting research methods for L2MSS research should not be an either/or choice: quantitative and qualitative designs can be chosen and, in some cases, combined in mixed methods approaches.

In recent years, there has been a call for an ethical agenda for L2 motivation research to align the field with more socially engaged and critically oriented approaches to research in applied linguistics (Ushioda, 2020). Ushioda (2020) argues that current L2 motivation research confines itself to individual psychological and associated pedagogical perspectives. Even studies that include social, political, and ideological dimensions are given superficial attention and are limited to descriptive characterizations of the context or setting in which the study took place or to specific external factors included as independent variables in the study, such as parental influence or cultural background. These drawbacks and the need to overcome them also apply specifically to L2MSS research.

Ushioda (2020) encourages future L2 motivation research to extend its primary focus to a macro-sociological perspective, taking on “the political and ideological structures affecting the motivations of individuals or communities to engage with other languages and cultures, or exposing social inequalities, barriers, or discriminatory practices where motivations to learn and use particular languages are critical issues” (p. 4). This new orientation of L2 motivation research is coined as the “Global South” perspective (Yousefi & Mahmoodi, 2022) and can also be taken up in L2MSS research. The Global South perspective focuses on struggles for transformation in a world that is unequal (Pennycook & Makoni, 2020). In this way, L2MSS research can become more diversified and shed new light on issues such as inequality, race, class, sexuality, poverty, gender, colonialism, immigration, and artificial intelligence, all of which impact learners’ motivation and daily lives.

IMPLICATIONS FOR LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

In his concluding remarks, Kikuchi (2019) points out that “without continuing rich L2 experiences and a personal goal to use English, learners in EFL situations have a hard time finding reasons to study” (p. 173). This conclusion highlights the importance of the L2MSS’s constructs, the future goal-oriented self and the L2 learning experience for L2 teaching and learning, particularly in EFL contexts.

For the future goal-oriented self, it is essential to help students envision themselves as competent future L2 users and understand the potential value of using a second/foreign language. These visions can guide their actions in engaging actively with their learning. In relation to classroom practice, Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) outline a six-phase vision-centred teaching framework which includes: “creating the language learner’s vision, strengthening the vision through imagery enhancement, substantiating the vision by making it plausible, transforming the vision into action, keeping the vision alive and counterbalancing the vision by considering failure” (p. 32). Several empirical studies (Hessel, 2015; Safdari, 2021; Sato, 2021; Sato & Lara, 2019; Vlaeva & Dörnyei, 2021; You et al., 2016) have supported the pedagogical benefits of focussing on learners’ visions. For example, in Gundarina’s (2023) study, drawing was successfully utilized as a classroom activity for migrant children to imagine their ideal selves, such as dreams about speaking English and future occupations. Such vision-enhancing classroom activities may be of particular value in EFL settings where L2 learners do not have as many opportunities to experience genuine interactions with L2 communities.

The second L2MSS construct, L2 Learning Experience, also has ramifications for language teaching and learning. While the future L2 self uses learners’ vision and imagination to motivate them to learn, the L2 Learning Experience focuses on the immediate learning environment, which can be complex and dynamic. Classrooms, particularly in EFL settings, are important for language learning. The important influence of classroom contexts on students’ motivation has been discussed in Dörnyei (1994), and later, Dörnyei (2001) highlighted motivational strategies that teachers could use in the classroom. Teachers need to understand the dynamic and temporal nature of students’ motivation. In Mercer’s (2022) words, “the motivation to begin studying a language is qualitatively and conceptually not the same as the motivation to engage in a specific classroom task” (p. 42). Also, in order to engage students in authentic and meaningful learning, teachers need to understand the motivational function of learning tasks in class. For example, task-

based learning (Ahmadian, 2016; Ellis, 2017; Van den Branden, 2016), which focuses on bringing real-world language activities into the classroom, and project-based learning (Gibbes & Carson, 2014; Kurt & Beck, 2023; Musa et al., 2011), which involves students designing solution real-world problems, both focus on meaningful interactions. Approaches such as these can be important strategies for fostering student engagement.

Mercer and Dörnyei (2020) provide a tripartite model of classroom engagement that integrates three interconnected components: willingness to engage, triggering engagement, and maintaining engagement. This model intends to support teachers in maximizing student engagement. Willingness to engage is a prerequisite for the other two components of this model. For willingness to engage, a teacher can pay attention to setting up learning environments that encourage positive learner mindsets, teacher-student relationships and group dynamics. An accepting and cooperative environment is essential for students to feel part of a group. As group relations (e.g., accepting, knowing one another, cooperating, competing, respecting individual space) emerge through interactions between students (with the teacher's guidance), a supportive and cooperative classroom can be established. This learning environment can enhance students' willingness to engage. For example, students should not feel threatened or embarrassed by making mistakes. Rather, they need to learn that making mistakes is a natural part of the L2 learning process. Willingness does not, however, necessarily guarantee engagement. It is also important for teachers to understand how to trigger engagement. Thus, the design and set-up of learning activities play a role in capturing learners' situational interest, attention and curiosity. In order to maintain engagement, these activities also need to be interactive and relevant to the learners and need to aim to develop learners' autonomy.

The above implications for teaching, however, are only suggestions, not fixed guidelines for language teachers to follow, as there is no one-size-fits-all solution. There are always limitations faced by teachers, such as, to name a few, social and cultural values in certain learning contexts and practical and logistical issues. These suggestions, however, can raise awareness among teachers of the inherent complexity and dynamic nature of students' L2 selves and L2 motivation in instructional L2 learning environments and can provide possible motivational teaching strategies to apply in these environments.

CONCLUSION

This article has critically discussed the L2MSS. This discussion has identified both the innovative contributions of the L2MSS to L2 motivation research and key issues associated with this theoretical model. This discussion has also highlighted directions for future research and implications for teaching practice. It is not the intention of this discussion to discredit the L2MSS. Rather, the discussion highlights the potential of the L2MSS to forge valuable links with the complex systems perspective that is currently breaking ground in L2 research (Chong et al., 2023). The L2MSS can potentially reflect the complexity of L2 motivation, as “any state of being or becoming is always in relation or seen as nodes in larger interconnected webs of human and social functioning” (Hiver & Larsen-Freeman, 2020, p. 298). The L2MSS can provide a rich, in-depth conceptualization of motivation that teachers can draw on in their pedagogical practices.

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REFERENCES

- Ahmadian, M. J. (2016). Task-based language teaching and learning. *The Language Learning Journal*, 44(4), 377–380.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2016.1236523>
- Al-Hoorie, A. H. (2018). The L2 motivational self system: A meta-analysis. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 8(4), 721–754.
<https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2018.8.4.2>

- Al-Hoorie, A. H., & Hiver, P. (2022). Complexity theory: From metaphors to methodological advances. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 175–184). Bloomsbury.
- Al-Hoorie, A. H., Hiver, P., & In'nami, Y. (2023). The validation crisis in the L2 motivational self system tradition. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 46(2), 307–329. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263123000487>
- Al-Hoorie, A. H., & Szabó, F. (2022). *Researching language learning motivation: A concise guide*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Al-Murtadha, M. (2019). Enhancing EFL learners' willingness to communicate with visualization and goal-setting activities. *TESOL Quarterly*, 53(1), 133–157. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.474>
- Alamer, A. (2024). Motivation and Language Learning. *Reference Module in Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-95504-1.00223-4>
- Boo, Z., Dörnyei, Z., & Ryan, S. (2015). L2 motivation research 2005–2014: Understanding a publication surge and a changing landscape. *System*, 55, 145–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.10.006>
- Busse, V. (2017). Plurilingualism in Europe: Exploring attitudes toward English and other European languages among adolescents in Bulgaria, Germany, the Netherlands, and Spain. *The Modern Language Journal*, 101(3), 566–582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12415>
- Chong, S. W., Isaacs, T., & McKinley, J. (2023). Ecological systems theory and second language research. *Language Teaching*, 56(3), 333–348. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444822000283>
- Consoli, S. (2024). What motivates Chinese students to study in the UK? A fresh perspective through a 'small-lens'. *Higher Education*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-024-01184-3>
- Csizér, K. (2019). The L2 motivational self system. In M. Lamb, C. Kata, H. Alastair, & R. Stephen (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of motivation for language learning* (pp. 71–93). Springer.

- Doiz, A., & Lasagabaster, D. (2018). Teachers' and students' second language motivational self system in English-medium instruction: A qualitative approach. *TESOL Quarterly*, 52(3), 657–679.
- Dörnyei, Z. (1994). Motivation and motivating in the foreign language classroom. *The Modern Language Journal*, 78(3), 273–284.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/330107>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2001). *Motivational strategies in the language classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2009). The L2 motivational self system. In Z. Dörnyei & E. Ushioda (Eds.), *Motivation, language identity and the L2 self* (pp. 9–42). Multilingual Matters.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2010). Researching motivation: From integrativeness to the ideal L2 self. *Introducing Applied Linguistics: Concepts and Skills*, 3(5), 74–83.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2019). Towards a better understanding of the L2 learning experience, the Cinderella of the L2 motivational self system. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(1), 19–30.
<https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2019.9.1.2>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2020). *Innovations and challenges in language learning motivation*. Routledge.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Chan, L. (2013). Motivation and vision: An analysis of future L2 self images, sensory styles, and imagery capacity across two target languages. *Language Learning*, 63(3), 437–462.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Kubanyiova, M. (2014). *Motivating learners, motivating teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ottó, I. (1998). Motivation in action: A process model of L2 motivation. *Working Papers in Applied Linguistics*, 47, 173–210.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (2011). *Teaching and researching motivation* (2nd ed.). Pearson Education.

- Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (2021). *Teaching and researching motivation* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Ellis, R. (2017). Task-based language teaching. In S. Loewen & M. Sato (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of instructed second language acquisition* (pp. 108–125). Routledge.
- Fryer, M., & Roger, P. (2018). Transformations in the L2 self: Changing motivation in a study abroad context. *System*, 78, 159–172.
- García, O. (2022). Too much psychology? The role of the social in language learning motivation. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation: A concise guide* (pp. 27–35). Bloomsbury.
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. Edward Arnold.
- Gibbes, M., & Carson, L. (2014). Project-based language learning: An activity theory analysis. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 8(2), 171–189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2013.793689>
- Gregersen, T., & MacIntyre, P. D. (2014). *Capitalizing on learners' individuality: From premise to practice*. Multilingual Matters.
- Gundarina, O. (2023). Migrant pupils as motivated agents: A qualitative longitudinal multiple-case study of Russian-speaking pupils' future ideal selves in English primary schools. *The Language Learning Journal*, 51(6), 749–765. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2022.2073383>
- Hadfield, J., & Dörnyei, Z. (2013). *Motivating learning*. Pearson.
- Henry, A. (2017). L2 motivation and multilingual identities. *The Modern Language Journal*, 101(3), 548–565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12412>
- Henry, A., & Liu, M. (2023). Can L2 motivation be modelled as a self-system? A critical assessment. *System*, 119, 103158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2023.103158>

- Henry, A., & Liu, M. (2024). Jingle-jangle fallacies in L2 motivational self system research: A response to Al-Hoorie et al.(2024). *Applied Linguistics*, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amae041>
- Hessel, G. (2015). From vision to action: Inquiring into the conditions for the motivational capacity of ideal second language selves. *System*, 52, 103-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.05.008>
- Higgins, E. T. (1987). Self-discrepancy: A theory relating self and affect. *Psychological Review*, 94(3), 319-340. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.94.3.319>
- Higgins, E. T. (1998). Promotion and prevention: regulatory focus as a motivational principle. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 30, 1-46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60381-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60381-0)
- Hiver, P. (2022). Engaging the learner: Linking teaching practice to learners' engagement and development. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 51-59). Bloomsbury.
- Hiver, P., & Al-Hoorie, A. H. (2020). *Research methods for complexity theory in applied linguistics*. Multilingual Matters.
- Hiver, P., & Larsen-Freeman, D. (2020). Motivation: It is a relational system. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & P. D. MacIntyre (Eds.), *Contemporary language motivation theory: 60 years since Gardner and Lambert (1959)* (pp. 285-303). Multilingual Matters.
- Hiver, P., Larsen-Freeman, D., Al-Hoorie, A. H., & Lowie, W. (2023). Complex dynamic systems and language education: A sampling of current research. *International Journal of Complexity in Education*, 4(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.26262/IJCE.V4I1.9476>
- Huang, H.-T., Hsu, C.-C., & Chen, S.-W. (2015). Identification with social role obligations, possible selves, and L2 motivation in foreign language learning. *System*, 51, 28-38. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.03.003>

- Irgatoğlu, A. (2021). L2 motivational self system and learning approaches of high school students. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.243>
- Kikuchi, K. (2019). Motivation and demotivation over two years: A case study of English language learners in Japan. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(1), 157–175. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssl.2019.9.1.7>
- Kurt, S., & Beck, J. (2023). Project-based language learning in Turkey, Greece, and Cyprus: A systematic review. *Journal of Language Teaching*, 3(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.54475/jlt.2023.001>
- Lamb, M. (2016). Motivation In G. Hall (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of English language teaching* (pp. 324–338). Routledge.
- Li, S., Prior, M., Nero, S., Hiver, P., Al-Hoorie, A. H., Murakami, A., Wei, L., & Ortega, L. (2023). Methodological innovation in applied linguistics research: Perspectives, strategies, and trends. *Language Teaching*, 56(4), 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S026144482300023X>
- Li, Z. (2023). The development and validation of a scale for measuring L2 learning experience: The underappreciated element of the L2 motivational self system. *Journal of Multilingual And Multicultural Development*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2023.2241854>
- MacIntyre, P. D. (2022). Using the self as a basis for a motivation system: Is it worth the trouble? In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 83–90). Bloomsbury.
- MacIntyre, P. D., Baker, S. C., & Sparling, H. (2017). Heritage passions, heritage convictions, and the rooted L2 self: Music and Gaelic language learning in Cape Breton, Nova Scotia. *The Modern Language Journal*, 101(3), 501–516. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12417>
- MacIntyre, P. D., & Serroul, A. (2015). Motivation on a per-second timescale: Examining approach-avoidance motivation during L2 task performance. In Z. Dörnyei, P. D. MacIntyre, & A. Henry (Eds.), *Motivational dynamics in language learning* (pp. 109–138). Multilingual Matters.

- Mackay, J. (2019). An ideal second language self intervention: Development of possible selves in an English as a Foreign Language classroom context. *System*, 81, 50–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.01.003>
- Markus, H., & Nurius, P. (1986). Possible selves. *American Psychologist*, 41(9), 954–969. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.41.9.954>
- Markus, H., & Wurf, E. (1987). The dynamic self-concept: A social psychological perspective. *Annual review of psychology*, 38(1), 299–337.
- Mercer, S. (2011). *Towards an Understanding of Language Learner Self-Concept* (Vol. 12). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Mercer, S. (2012). The challenges of researching the self as a complex dynamic system. *ELT Research*, 27, 18–21.
- Mercer, S. (2022). Engagement: The active ingredient in language learning. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (Vol. , pp. 39–50). Bloomsbury.
- Mercer, S., & Dörnyei, Z. (2020). *Engaging language learners in contemporary classrooms*. Cambridge University Press.
- Musa, F., Mufti, N., Latiff, R. A., & Amin, M. M. (2011). Project-based learning: Promoting meaningful language learning for workplace skills. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 18, 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.05.027>
- Noels, K. A. (2001). New orientations in language learning motivation: Towards a model of intrinsic, extrinsic, and integrative orientations and motivation. In Z. Dörnyei & R. Schmidt (Eds.), *Motivation and second language acquisition* (pp. 43–68). University of Hawaii.
- Oga-Baldwin, W. Q., & Hirosawa, E. (2022). Self-determined motivation and engagement in language: A dialogic process. In A. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 71–80). Bloomsbury.
- Papi, M. (2022). The L2 motivational self system: Using the selves in th classroom. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 91–98). Bloomsbury.

- Papi, M., Bondarenko, A. V., Mansouri, S., Feng, L., & Jiang, C. (2019). Rethinking L2 motivation research: The 2× 2 model of L2 self-guides. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 41(2), 337-361.
- Papi, M., & Hiver, P. (2020). Language learning motivation as a complex dynamic system: A global perspective of truth, control and value. *Modern Language Journal*, 104(1), 1-59. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12624>
- Pennycook, A., & Makoni, S. (2020). *Innovations and challenges in applied linguistics from the global south*. Routledge.
- Poehner, M. E. (2022). Motivation, mediation, and the individual: A sociocultural theory perspective. In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 17-26). Bloomsbury.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78.
- Safdari, S. (2021). Operationalizing L2 motivational self system: Improving EFL learners' motivation through a vision enhancement program. *Language Teaching Research*, 25(2), 282-305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168819846597>
- Sato, M. (2021). Generating a roadmap for possible selves via a vision intervention: Alignment of second language motivation and classroom behavior. *TESOL Quarterly*, 55(2), 427-457. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.611>
- Sato, M., & Lara, P. (2019). Interaction vision intervention to increase second language motivation: A classroom study. In *Evidence-based second language pedagogy* (pp. 287-313). Routledge.
- Tajabadi, A., & Consoli, S. (2024). Understanding language learning motivation from a dual analytical lens: Combining activity theory and life capital. *TESOL Quarterly*, 0(0), 0000. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3367>
- Thompson, A. S. (2017). Don't tell me what to do! The anti-ought-to self and language learning motivation. *System*, 67, 38-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2017.04.004>

- Ushioda, E. (2009). A person-in-context relational view of emergent motivation, self and identity. In Z. Dörnyei & E. Ushioda (Eds.), *Motivation, Language Identity and the L2 Self* (pp. 215-228). Multilingual Matters.
- Ushioda, E. (2016). Language learning motivation through a small lens: A research agenda. *Language Teaching*, 49(4), 564–577.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444816000173>
- Ushioda, E. (2020). *Language learning motivation*. Oxford University Press.
- Ushioda, E. (2022). Motivating in the language classroom: A discourse of “social control”? In A. H. Al-Hoorie & F. Szabó (Eds.), *Researching language learning motivation* (pp. 7–16). Bloomsbury.
- Van den Branden, K. (2016). Task-based language teaching. In G. Hall (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of English language teaching* (pp. 238–251). Routledge.
- Vlaeva, D., & Dörnyei, Z. (2021). Vision enhancement and language learning: A critical analysis of vision-building in an English for Academic Purposes programme. *Language Teaching Research*, 0(0), 1–26.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688211014551>
- Wang, T., & Liu, Y. (2017). Dynamic L3 selves: A longitudinal study of five university L3 learners’ motivational trajectories in China. *The Language Learning Journal*, 1–12.
- Wang, W. (2022). Effects of online L2 learning experiences on L2 selves. *Journal of Pan-Pacific Association of Applied Linguistics*, 26(1), 21–38.
<https://doi.org/10.25256/PAAL.26.1.2>
- Yang, L., & Liang-Itsara, A. (2024). Thai undergraduates’ motivation in learning different foreign languages: A Dörnyei’s L2MSS perspective. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 23(1), 159–185.
<https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.23.1.9>
- You, C., Dörnyei, Z., & Csizér, K. (2016). Motivation, vision, and gender: A survey of learners of English in China. *Language Learning*, 66(1), 94–123.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12410>

Yousefi, M., & Mahmoodi, M. H. (2022). The L2 motivational self-system: A meta-analysis approach. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijal.12416>